

June 2021

Press Release

Open Call#2 for Accelerating Data-Driven Solutions to Save LIVES from COVID-19

The consortium of **COVID-X** announces the launch of **Open Call #2** for a unique acceleration programme in Europe to fast-track to market **15+ European data technology solutions**, addressing COVID-19 challenges and facilitating an innovative stack of AI-driven tools in order to defeat the pandemic.

COVID-X Programme, supported by the European Commission under Horizon2020 programme, **funds European companies and healthcare providers to boost 30+ data-driven solutions to the markets to overcome clinical challenges in diagnosis, prognosis, and follow-up**. The funding is invested in solutions with TRL 7+ and [or in the process of] CE marking, covering two profiles: single solution (EU tech SMEs / Start-Ups) validating their solutions at one of COVID-X pilot sites; or team solution (Tech provider bringing in a healthcare provider that will validate the solution).

In addition to the direct funding, the COVID-X Programme **provides the top-ranked solutions access in a tailored acceleration programme** organized in 3 sprints of 3 months each. These include technical coaching, business mentoring sessions as well as support in ethical issues and piloting with healthcare organizations. This 10-month programme targets to boost the quick market uptake to defeat COVID-19 with data solutions.

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To attract top-notch solutions meeting the set selection criteria, **the Open Call#2 has a two-stage application process:** In the first stage, the applicant's eligibility and alignment with the selection criteria are assessed. All eligible applications access the 2nd stage where the complete application form with detailed information about the solution & implementation is required.

The COVID-X Programme Open Call #1 closed on 27.1.2021 gathering 112 applications from data technology companies and healthcare providers coming from 29 different countries in Europe and beyond. **16 selected single and team solutions were selected and are now completing the 1st Sprint of the programme.**

The Open Call#2 application is now open in this [link](#) and the **deadline** for the first stage will be on **the 22nd of July 2021. (17:00PM CEST).**

COVID-X involves a consortium of 10 prominent partners from 7 different countries:

CIVITTA

HUMANITAS
RESEARCH HOSPITAL

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